

STIMULATING PUPILS' INTEREST IN LEARNING THE MOTHER TONGUE THROUGH LITERARY WORKS

G.A. Mamatova

Associate Professor, PhD, Department of Preschool and Primary Education, PROFI University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21028815>

Abstract. *This article addresses the problem of fostering primary school pupils' love for learning their mother tongue through literary works in mother-tongue lessons. On the basis of practical classroom experience, the article discusses the specific features of teaching third-grade pupils to use literary texts while studying the lexical and grammatical characteristics of the verb as a part of speech.*

Keywords: *mother tongue, linguistic phenomena, motivation, parts of speech, verb, didactic material, literary text, visual means, expressive means.*

Introduction

As usual, after an ordinary working day, I was returning home from work by bus. The bus was very crowded. At the next stop, a little girl and a boy, about five or six years old, boarded the bus with their mothers after returning from kindergarten. Seeing that they were being squeezed among the passengers, I brought them closer to me. On the way, they began talking to one another about something. During the conversation, the girl angrily said a very unpleasant phrase in Russian to the boy. At that moment, perhaps remembering that I was standing behind them and observing the situation, the girl turned to me and said, 'Auntie, did I do it well?' I explained to her that she had not done a good thing, that she herself was a beautiful little girl, but that the words she had used were very ugly. I told her that from then on she should speak beautifully not in Russian, but in her own mother tongue. I was astonished by her reply: 'Auntie, I know Uzbek, I know Russian, but I do not know my mother tongue.' I explained to her that every nation has its own mother tongue, that the mother tongue of the Uzbek nation is the Uzbek language, and that Uzbek is therefore her own mother tongue. At this, the girl's eyes lit up, and she joyfully said, 'Then I do know my mother tongue.'

After this incident, I began to reflect. To what extent are preschool educators and primary school teachers able to convey to the younger generation the concept of the mother tongue and its significance? Are they able to explain that the mother tongue is one of our national values?

Language is a great blessing. Language is the pride, dignity, and mirror of a nation. Since language is one of the main features that distinguishes nations from one another, every person must know and honor his or her mother tongue while also respecting the mother tongues of other nations.

The great scholar Alikhantora Soguniy wrote the following in his book *The Sorrow of Turkestan*: 'In order not to forget one's identity, a person must not lose three things: homeland, religion, and language.'

The mother tongue is the mirror of a nation's spirit, culture, and historical memory. Love for the mother tongue is a practical expression of self-awareness, devotion to the homeland, and deep respect for the heritage of one's ancestors.

Unfortunately, as a result of certain factors, the younger generation's enthusiasm for studying the mother tongue and literature has weakened. The level of literacy is also a matter of concern. This is a great tragedy for the development of a nation, because when the children of a country stop reading in their mother tongue, that language sinks into the depths of disappearance. Protecting it from alien influences determines the future of the nation. Therefore, each of us must approach our language with deep respect in order to raise the prestige of our mother tongue at the international level and to bring it into the ranks of developed languages based on both national and universal concepts.

In this regard, the following words of our enlightened ancestor Ishokhon Ibrat, who mastered nearly ten world languages in his time, are especially noteworthy: 'Our young people should certainly strive to learn other languages, but first they should cherish their own mother tongue as something precious and show it respect. Indeed, loyalty to one's own language is a patriotic duty.'

Thus, the question remains: to what extent are preschool educators and primary school teachers able to communicate to the future generation the concept and significance of the mother tongue, and to explain that the mother tongue is one of our national values?

In our research, we decided to approach this problem from a linguo-methodological perspective. What is the current level of pupils' interest in studying the subject of the mother tongue? How successfully are primary school teachers fulfilling this task? What didactic materials do they use in mother-tongue lessons to increase pupils' motivation? In this article, we attempt to answer these questions.

The Literary Text as Didactic Material in Mother-Tongue Lessons

A literary text used as didactic material in a mother-tongue lesson is not merely a tool for encouraging children to think formally when analyzing individual words, word combinations, and sentences. Rather, it is a means of systematically teaching them to use linguistic resources creatively, developing linguistic competence, and understanding the style of a writer or poet.

Mother-tongue textbooks certainly provide high-quality didactic material in various exercises. These materials are mainly selected from classical Uzbek literature and examples of oral folklore. However, every teacher should select his or her own didactic material for a specific lesson, because the choice of material for the topic being studied and its methodologically correct use in mother-tongue lessons are of great importance.

When selecting didactic material for a particular lesson, the teacher should think carefully about the system of working with a literary text during the lesson. As a rule, this involves analyzing texts from the point of view of speech style and type, theme, idea, and visual and expressive means. In addition, different types of linguistic analysis may be carried out in the lesson, including orthoepic, phonetic, morphemic, morphological, and syntactic analysis; the words selected for analysis are also taken from the literary text.

When a particular linguistic phenomenon is studied in a mother-tongue lesson, working with texts from literary works that have recently been studied, or are still being studied, in reading-literacy lessons produces highly effective results. Pupils find it interesting to work with familiar works, recognize the characters, recall the events, and once again discuss the theme and idea of the work, but from a slightly different perspective: by analyzing the linguistic features of the literary work and identifying the stylistic characteristics of a particular writer or poet.

Below are several examples of how texts from fiction may be used in mother-tongue lessons.

Example of Classroom Application

Mother-tongue lesson. Grade 3. Topic: Affirmative and Negative Verbs. All didactic materials required for teaching this topic were selected on the basis of the text Yaxshilik (Goodness), which had recently been studied in the Reading Literacy lesson.

Explaining the new material

Observation of sentences presented on a slide, on cards, or on the board.

Read the sentences:

Fazliddin was playing in the street with his friend Nabi. I help my grandfather Normamat. Grandfather Normamat loves me. Fazliddin ran to Grandfather Normamat. Grandfather Normamat took the bundle from Fazliddin's hand. However, as he usually did, he did not praise him. His friend ran up to him. Fazliddin did not raise his head.

- From which work are these lines taken? (Farhod Musajonov, Yaxshilik / Goodness).
- Whom are these lines about? (They are about Fazliddin and Grandfather Normamat).

The teacher may also remind pupils of the genre of the work, Fazliddin and the lesson he learned, and other related details.

Ask questions about the highlighted verbs and write them side by side. Identify the difference between the questions asked about the verbs. This work may be done on the board and in pupils' notebooks:

Verb form	Question	Grammatical meaning
was playing	What was he doing?	indicates an action performed
help	What do I do?	indicates an action performed
loves	What does he do?	indicates an action performed
ran to	What did he do?	indicates an action performed
took	What did he do?	indicates an action performed
did not praise	What did he not do?	indicates an action not performed
ran up	What did he do?	indicates an action performed
did not raise	What did he not do?	indicates an action not performed

What difference do we observe?

The verbs was playing, help, loves, ran to, took, and ran up indicate actions that were performed. The verbs did not praise and did not raise indicate actions that were not performed. In Uzbek, the negative verb form that expresses an action not performed contains the suffix -ma.

Definition: Verbs that indicate the performance of an action are called affirmative verbs. Verbs that indicate that an action was not performed are called negative verbs. Negative verbs are formed with the suffix -ma. At this point, the definitions of affirmative and negative verbs may appear on the screen. In primary grades, negation is taught only through the method of affixation.

Demonstrating the application of knowledge in similar conditions

If we need to determine whether a verb is affirmative or negative, how should we proceed? At this stage, the teacher and pupils develop an algorithm.

Now we will identify together the affirmative and negative verbs in the following sentences. The text should be displayed on the screen in advance.

Independent work. The text appears on the screen. Task: insert the missing verb suffixes and determine whether the verbs are affirmative or negative.

Fazliddin did not boast to his friend. I always help elderly people. Believe me, come with me and see for yourself. Grandfather Normamat heard Fazliddin's words. Fazliddin ran to the grandfather. Grandfather Normamat whispered into Fazliddin's ear.

Pupils write the sentences, insert the missing suffixes, and, by applying the algorithm, identify the affirmative and negative verbs in the text.

When working with these short texts, pupils recall the characters of the story together with the teacher: Fazliddin, Grandfather Normamat, and Nabi. They are the pupils' peers. Naturally, the idea of the work is emphasized once again: do good, but do not erase it through boasting.

Conclusion

On the basis of the points discussed above, it is necessary once again to emphasize the importance of didactic material in teaching any topic in mother-tongue lessons. For primary school teachers, well-selected didactic material consisting of texts from the works of Uzbek writers and poets is one of the main conditions for organizing an effective lesson. It may be regarded both as a model of the mother tongue and as a means of developing pupils' creative abilities.

The connection between the linguistic material studied in mother-tongue lessons and the literary works read and analyzed in literature or reading lessons helps pupils better understand the secrets of language and become familiar with literature as the art of the word.

Thus, the systematic use of literary texts in mother-tongue instruction strengthens pupils' motivation, supports the development of linguistic competence, and cultivates respect for the national language as a central cultural value. Literary texts make grammar more meaningful for young learners because linguistic forms are not studied in isolation; rather, they are examined within emotionally and culturally rich contexts that pupils already understand.

REFERENCES

1. Yo'ldoshev, M. (2008). *Badiiy matnning lisoniy tahlili* [Linguistic analysis of the literary text]. Samarkand: Samarkand State University Publishing House. 114 p.
2. Doniyorov, Kh., & Mirzayev, S. (1962). *So'z san'ati: Badiiy mahorat va til haqida mulohazalar* [The art of the word: Reflections on artistic mastery and language]. Tashkent: Fan.
3. Ergasheva, M. (2021). *Badiiy matn tahlili bo'yicha o'quv qo'llanma* [A study guide on literary text analysis]. Tashkent: Fan. 120 p.